

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF THE AK7-SiC COMPOSITES AFTER MACHINING

Jolanta Cyboron¹, Malgorzata Karolus¹, Piotr Putyra¹, Maciej Dyzia², Lucyna Jaworska¹

¹ Institute of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, Wroclawska 37a St. 30-011 Krakow, Poland
Email: jolanta.cyboron@ios.krakow.pl, malgorzata.karolus@ios.krakow.pl,
piotr.putyra@ios.krakow.pl, lucyna.jaworska@ios.krakow.pl, web page: www.ios.krakow.pl

² Department of Materials Technology, Silesian University of Technology, Krasińskiego 8 St., 40-019
Katowice, Poland
Email: maciej.dyzia@polsl.pl, web page: <http://inom.polsl.pl>

Keywords: Alumina composite, Silicon carbide, XRD analysis, Strain and stress, Rietveld refinement

ABSTRACT

The presented paper reports the structure and properties analyses of the AlSi7Mg/SiC composites obtained by stir casting (suspension) method. The aluminum matrix alloy contain different amount (5 and 10 vol. %) SiC reinforcement particles. The tested material was subjected to the machining process of Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM), the Abrasive Water Jet (WJ) and grinding, as well.

The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained by using the PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer with the copper radiation. The phase analysis was done using the ICDD (PDF4+ 2013) files. The quantitative phase analysis of studied composites was performed by the Rietveld refinement – using the High Score Plus PANalytical software. The residual stress calculation was performed by using the $g\text{-sin}^2\psi$ method.

The morphology of the materials was studied by the optical microscope (Neophot 2). In order to determine the physical and mechanical properties of the materials, the hardness, Young's modulus, the Poisson coefficient and density were measured.

The XRD analyses have shown that the tested aluminum matrix alloy with silicon carbide addition had non-homogeneous structure with different phase composition in materials layers depending on the X-ray penetration depth.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aluminum–silicon carbide composite (Al–SiC) is one of the most promising metal matrix composites for their specific properties like high strength and stiffness as well as low density [1]. These properties have made particle-reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) an attractive candidate for use in weight-sensitive and stiffness-critical components in aerospace, transportation and industrial sectors [2]. However, we should note that each of elements of these composites - aluminum and silicon carbide have different mechanical properties for example: linear coefficients of thermal expansion for Al is 23.1×10^{-6} and 2.77×10^{-6} K for SiC and Young's moduli 70 and 450 GPa for Al and SiC, respectively[3].

During the design composites we can encounter to a number of problems associated with differences between these materials especially, difficulty of achieving a uniform distribution silicon carbide reinforcement, wettability between ceramic and matrix and porosity in cast metal composites [4].

These are the reasons for which have to be specified all the parameters of the manufacturing process influencing on the structure and properties. Choosing the proper way of the manufacturing these composites substantially affect to the best properties.

The main purpose of this paper was to determine the influence of different methods of machining Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) and Abrasive Water Jet (WJ) on the phase composition, structure, physical and mechanical properties in the bulk composite material type AlSi7Mg with different amount of silicon carbide reinforcement particles. In order to this the grinding process was performed for both surfaces, as well. The values of the residual stresses obtained just after EDM and Water Jet machining and grinding processes were compared.

2 THE RESEARCH MATERIALS

Aluminum matrix composite with 5 vol.% and 10 vol.% silicon carbide addition were chosen as the tested material. The metal matrix were modified by adding magnesium and strontium. Process was conducted in two stages. Silicon carbide particles, with the grain size of 40-80 μm , were preheated in 350°C and next added to the liquid metal at 720 °C. In the second step, the suspension was placed in hermetic chamber which enabled proper degassing and homogenization under reduced pressure. Sample for presented studies were cut from the extruder piston (Fig.1).

Figure 1: The casting piston – scheme of the tested material (red line – grinded surface).

3 XRD MEASUREMENTS

The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained by using the PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer with the copper radiation ($\lambda_{\text{Cu}} = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The phase analyses were done using the ICDD (PDF-4+ 2013) files. The quantitative phase analysis of studied material was performed by the Rietveld refinement [5] – using the High Score Plus PANalytical software.

Such measurements were carried out, in different orientation of the specimen - short and long diagonals parallel to the primary beam direction (Fig.2), for surfaces obtained after Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM), Abrasive Water Jet (WJ) treatment and subsequently grinding.

Figure 2 : Tested areas: short and long diagonals parallel to the primary beam direction.

The results of phase composition after machining processes are presented in the table 1 - for material with 10 vol.% SiC and table 2 - for material with 5 vol.% SiC.

Initial machining	Phase composition	Space group	wt. %
EDM	Al	Fm-3m	60
	SiC-6H	P63mc	29
	SiC-4H	P63mc	8
	Si	Fd-3m	2
	Mg ₂ Si	Fm-3 m	1
Water Jet	Al	Fm-3m	64
	SiC-6H	P63mc	25
	SiC-4H	P63mc	7
	Si	Fd-3m	2
	Mg ₂ Si	Fm-3 m	2

Table 1 : Qualitative and quantitative phase analyses of the AlSi7Mg/10 vol.% SiC composite after machining.

Initial machining	Phase composition	Space group	wt. %
EDM	Al	Fm-3m	94
	SiC-6H	P63mc	1
	SiC-4H	P63mc	1
	Si	Fd-3m	3
	Mg ₂ Si	Fm-3 m	1
Water Jet	Al	Fm-3m	96
	SiC-6H	P63mc	1
	SiC-4H	P63mc	1
	Si	Fd-3m	1
	Mg ₂ Si	Fm-3 m	1

Table 2 : Qualitative and quantitative phase analyses of the AlSi7Mg/5 vol.% SiC composite after machining.

Figure 3 and 4 are shown the XRD patterns obtained for the composites containing 5 and 10 vol.% SiC.

Figure 3. The XRD pattern for the composite contains 5 vol.% SiC.

Figure 4. The XRD pattern for the composite contains 10 vol.% SiC.

The XRD phase analysis showed the presence of aluminum and a different polymorphic forms of silicon carbide phases (see: table 1 and 2).

4 STRESS DETERMINATION

The Grazing Incidence X-ray Diffraction is the method basing on the whole X-ray diffraction pattern analysis provided to the phase characterization of the material layers depending on the depth. For different values of the primary beam angle (α) there is possible to determine the residual stress values for layers of tested material, as well. The results of such analyses after machining methods for aluminum phase are presented in table 3 and 4.

XRD geometry	X-ray Penetration depth	Residual stress σ [MPa]		Residual stress σ [MPa]	
		EDM	Grinding	Water Jet	Grinding
B-B	up to 100 μm	-65.8	13.8	-336.9	26.4
GIXD, $\alpha = 1^\circ$	$\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$	-146.3	18.7	-223.1	95.3
GIXD, $\alpha = 3^\circ$	$\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$	88.2	-9.3	-224	-9.7

Table 3. The values of the residual stresses obtained for AlSi7Mg/10 vol.% SiC composite after machining.

For material containing 10 vol.% SiC just after EDM and Water Jet processes, residual stress values were shown different characters. For surface after EDM method they are changing. for whole volume of sample (BB geometry) - up to 100 μm , similar to the top layer around 3 μm , the residual stress values have shown a tensile character but for layer around 10 μm - these value was 88.2 MPa. For the surface material after Water Jet technique all layers have shown the same character – presence of tensile residual stresses. In comparison, after additional treatment – grinding, the character of the residual stress have been changed and the values become comparable for both surfaces (EDM and Water Jet) with the tensile characters.

XRD geometry	Penetration depth	Residual stress σ [MPa]		Residual stress σ [MPa]	
		EDM	Grinding	Water Jet	Grinding
B-B	up to 100 μm	-59.3	13.8	192.6	26.4

Table 4. The values of the residual stresses obtained for AlSi7Mg/5 vol.% SiC composite after machining.

For materials containing 5 vol.% SiC after EDM and Water Jet machining and grinding processes, the values of the residual stress determined basing on the whole X-ray diffraction pattern analysis ($g\text{-sin}^2\psi$) have shown similar effect. The values and character of the residual stresses were almost the same for both surfaces (EDM and WJ) after grinding. It indicates significant influence of machining processes on the state of studied materials.

5 MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE COMPOSITE

The morphology of the tested materials after machining, were studied by the optical microscope (Neophot 2). The microstructure of the selected sample surfaces are shown in Figures 5, 6.

Figure 5: Image of AlSi7Mg/5 vol.% SiC composite, mag.20x.

Figure 6 : Image of AlSi7Mg/10 vol.% SiC composite, mag.20x.

Images have shown non-homogeneous microstructure of materials with 5 vol. % of silicon carbide. Ceramic particles are arranged in aggregations. For materials with 10 vol.% of SiC, the microstructure analysis has shown that the distribution of the silicon carbide particles is quite regular. What is more, these studies confirm the phase composition analysis results, which detect much more higher content of ceramic reinforcement.

In both of composites the brighter areas visible on the microstructures images (Fig. 5,6) are correspond to AlSi7Mg alloy matrix, the darker places correspond to SiC phase.

6 PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Young's modules and Poisson coefficients were measured using the ultrasonic method (EPOCH 3, Panametrics). The densities were measured using hydrostatic method. The results are summarized in table 5.

Material	Poisson coefficient ν	Young's modulus E [GPa]	Density ρ [g/cm ³]	
			Theoretical (*)	Experimental
Al alloy	0.35	70	2.7	-
SiC	0.16	450	3.41	-
AlSi7Mg/5 %vol. SiC	0.33	72	2.74	2.65
AlSi7Mg/10 %vol. SiC	0.28	76	2.77	2.49

Table 5. Physical properties of AlSi7Mg/SiC composites (* [7,8]).

The tested materials were characterized by relatively low values of the Young's modulus. However, addition of SiC phase into the composite entail increasing these values to 72 [GPa] for 5 vol. % and 76 [GPa] for 10 vol. % SiC, respectively. Moreover, the densities were decreased in comparison to the theoretical values. It could be the result of occurring the substantial porosity in both kind of composites.

In case the fact that the XRD measurements was carried out in two different sample orientations - short diagonal or long diagonal parallel to the X-ray direction - the hardness measurements were conducted on cross sections with relation to these directions (Fig.7). Brinell hardness was performed according to the Polish Standard PN-EN ISO 6506-1 for Aluminium Alloys by Frankoskop optical hardness device using ball at diameter 2.5 mm and load of 612.9 N.

Figure 7: Geometries of the measurements: a) L - "long diagonal". b) S - "short diagonal".

Table 7 shows the Brinell hardness results obtained for composites with different reinforcement percentage. One can see that addition of the reinforcement particles entail increasing of the hardness in comparison to values characterized AlSi7Mg composite. Silicon carbide particles have very high hardness, around 2600 HV, so the reinforcing into the matrix material, helped to improve the hardness properties of composite by considerable amount.

Materials	Brinell hardness [HB]	
	Long diagonal	Short diagonal
Al alloys	~50	
AlSi7Mg/5 vol.% SiC	83.6 ± 1.2	85.6 ± 0.9
AlSi7Mg/10vol.% SiC	70.6 ± 1.2	71.6 ± 1.4

Table 7: Brinell hardness results obtained for composites based on aluminum matrix.

7 CONCLUSION

The effects of addition silicon carbide on the phase composition, microstructure, residual stress and physical and mechanical properties on aluminum matrix alloy were investigated.

Microstructure of tested samples had different characters for material contains 5 and 10 vol.% of SiC. For 5 vol.% SiC, the microstructure shown inhomogeneous distribution of ceramic particles. In that material, the silicon carbide particle created agglomeration. For composites containing 10 vol.% SiC, ceramic particles had more homogeneous distribution.

The XRD analyses showed presence of aluminum and Si-C phases in both of composites. Heterogeneity in these material produces great gradient of the residual stresses. These stresses values

decreasing in both of composite with increasing X-ray penetration depth. Comparison of the results obtained before (directly after EDM and Water Jet machining) and after grinding processes shown that the character of the residual stress were changing. Furthermore the residual stress results obtained after grinding were comparable. For material contains 10 vol.% of SiC addition in the layers around 10 μm these values were around -9 MPa.

The Young's moduli of AlSi7Mg/SiC were higher than values characterized aluminum alloys - 72 and 76 GPa for 5 vol.% and 10 vol.% SiC, respectively. The composite densities were lower values than theoretical ones. For material contains 5 vol.% of SiC it was 2.65 and for material with 10 vol.% SiC - 2.49 g/cm^3 .

The tested materials were characterized by relatively low hardness. Moreover, the results of the Brinell hardness for materials contain SiC addition are greater than values characterized aluminum alloys: 83.6 and 70.6 HB, respectively. There are no significant differences in results of the hardness obtained for the "long" and "short" diagonals. It might be the effect of the macro scale measurements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Applied Research Programme : " Opracowanie składu fazowego kompozytów na bazie stopu AlSi pod kątem możliwości kształtowania powierzchni roboczych tłoków", KOMPCAST, Nr PBS1/B6/13/2013.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Rosso, Ceramic and metal matrix composites: routes and properties, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 175, no. 1–3, 2006, pp. 364–375.
- [2] J. Sobczak, S. Wojciechowski, The current trends in the practical application of metal matrix composites, *Composites*, 2, 2002, pp. 24-37 (http://composites.ptmk.net/pliczki/pliki/semVI_3.pdf).
- [3] E.Hatch, Aluminium - Properties and Physical Metallurgy, *American Society for Metals, Metals Park*, Ohio, 1984.
- [4] J.Hashim, L.Looney, M.S.J. Hashami, Metal Matrix composites: production by stir casting method, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 92-93, 1999, pp. 1-7.
- [5] L.B. McCusker, R.B.VonDreele., E.D. Cox, D.Louer, P. Scardi , Rietveld refinement guidelines: *J Appl Crystallogr*, 32, 1999, pp.36-50.
- [6] H.Mändar, J.Felshe, V.Mikli, T.Vajakas, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 32, 1999, pp.345-350.
- [7] Vargel Ch., Corrosion of Aluminium, Elsevier 2004, part A.1, A.3, B.2.
- [8] Riedel R., Handbook of Ceramic Hard Materials, Volume 1, p.683-688.